

This table includes questions and recommendations music librarians can use to assess vinyl records for their collections.

Table 2. Criteria to consider when recommending LPs for a collection.

Question	Recommendation	Related literature
Does the library have alternative access to this recording (CD, streaming audio)? Alternatively, is this a rare or unique recording?	If the library has access to this recording elsewhere, we do not need it as an LP.	Imre & Cox (2009) Smith (2012)
Does this recording have particular production value?	If the recording has specific production value, we will consider adding it to the collection.	
Is this a high-quality LP? ('Very good plus' to 'mint' grade.)	We tend to exclude LPs that are not of very high quality, since the number of LPs in storage is so high.	Imre & Cox (2009) Prince (2020)
Does this LP have unique artwork or is its artwork representative of a certain style or genre?	Album artwork is an important aspect of a LP, so unique artwork or representative styles should be included in the collection.	Smith (2012) Austin (2017) Shepherd & Leonard (2014) Wolf (2018)
Is this LP relevant to undergraduate curricula?	This criterion may justify including recordings by composers whose work is otherwise available.	Imre & Cox (2009) Smith (2012)
Is this LP relevant to faculty and graduate research?	This criterion may also justify including recordings by composers available in other formats.	Schultz (2020) Smith (2012) Czeisel (2021)
Does this LP have local significance?	If a LP has local significance, consider adding it to the collection even if it is of lower quality, irrelevant to curriculum, or the library has access to the recording via a different format.	Imre & Cox (2009) Smith (2012)
Does the collection development policy recommend including this LP?	Final decisions should be made with the collection development policy in mind. If the collection aims to feature interdisciplinary artifacts, it should favour LPs with	Smith (2012)

	high multimedia value (interesting artwork, notes, high production value).	
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References

- Austin, J. (Ed.). (2017). *Spinning popular culture as public pedagogy*. SensePublishers.
- Czeisel, M. J., & Smith, V. D. (2021). University music students' choice of music listening sources: Use of library resources as compared with non-academic streaming services. *Music Reference Services Quarterly*, 24(4), 194–220.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10588167.2020.1854568>
- Imre, A., & Cox, E. J. (2009). Are we on the right track? Issues with LP recording collections in U.S. academic libraries. *Notes*, 65(3), 475–486. <https://doi.org/10.1353/not.0.0116>
- Prince, P. (2020). Record grading 101: Understanding the Goldmine grading guide. Goldmine: The music collector's magazine. Accessed 19 December 2022 from <https://www.goldminemag.com/collector-resources/LP-grading-101>
- Schultz, W. (2020). Weeding a music collection for the first time: A common sense approach. *Music Reference Services Quarterly*, 23(3–4), 119–129.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10588167.2020.1814527>
- Shepherd, T., Leonard, A. (Eds.). (2014). *The Routledge companion to music and visual culture*. Routledge.
- Smith, S. (2012). Weeding considerations for an academic music collection. *Music Reference Services Quarterly*, 15(1), 22–33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10588167.2012.647601>
- Wolf, M. (Ed.). (2018). *The Routledge companion to media technology and obsolescence*. Routledge.